

Psychoemotional and cognitive disorders in chronic cerebral ischemia

Adhamova M.A.

Scientific supervisor: Majidova Ya.N., Azimova N.M.

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute.

The purpose of the study was an assessment of the cognitive and psychoemotional sphere in patients with chronic cerebral ischemia.

Materials and research methods: The study included 40 patients with stage 1-2 CCI aged from 50 to 65 years, with a predominance of men over women (22 (55%) versus 18 (45%)). Clinical symptoms in 13 (32.5%) patients corresponded to stage 1 CCI, in 27 (67.5%) patients - stage 2 CCI with mild and moderate cognitive impairment (DSM5 classification). The state of the cognitive sphere was studied using a short test for assessing the mental sphere - Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), which allows quantitative assessment of general cognitive deficit. To assess the severity of psycho-emotional disorders, the Beck Anxiety Scale (BAS) and the Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS) were used.

Research results: During observation, in patients with stage 1 CCI, the total MMSE score was 27.8 ± 0.41 points, while in the group of patients with stage 2 CCI it was 23.6 ± 0.09 points. At the time of inclusion in the study, all patients showed disturbances in the emotional sphere. A study of the psycho-emotional state using clinical depression scales showed that depressive syndrome is typical in the group of patients with CCI: the average score of anxiety disorders on the Beck Anxiety Scale in the group of patients with CCI stage 2 was 9.2 ± 2.1 , which corresponds to Beck slight anxiety, whereas in the group with stage 1 CCI - 7.1 ± 1.4 points. The results on the Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS) averaged 13.3 ± 2.1 points in the group with stage 2 CCI, which corresponds to mild depression, while in the group of patients with stage 1 CCI it was 9.3 ± 2.1 points.

Conclusions: with CCI, an increase in neurological symptoms is combined with a worsening of cognitive and depressive disorders. The development of cognitive and depressive disorders correlates with more extensive focal brain damage and more pronounced vascular disorders.

Literature:

1. Antipenko E.A., Deryugina A.V., A.V. Gustov Systemic stress-limiting effect of mexidol in chronic ischemia of the brain // S.S. Korsakov Journal of Neurology and Psychiatry, No 4, 2016, pp. 28-31
2. Voronina T.A. Pioneer of antioxidant neuroprotection. 20 years in clinical practice // Russian Medical Journal. Neurology, No1, 2016.
3. Zakharov V.V. et al. Chronic Cerebral Circulation Insufficiency: A Description of a Clinical Case // Therapeutic Archive, No4, 2016, pp.93-98